

SAFETY AND SECURITY OF PARAGLIDING AS A RECREATIONAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to raise awareness of the safety and security of paragliding as a recreational activity to enhance and promote the tourism industry in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. The study utilized a qualitative descriptive approach, which involved conducting a site visit and group interviews using an interview guide. This was carried out with a cohort of nine proficient pilots who are actively engaged in operations at the paragliding site. Risk factors such as flying with low-level skills and accountability, poor knowledge of weather and terrain conditions, and inadequate strength and weight were significant dangers in paragliding. Safety precautions before, during, and after flights were found to be crucial, requiring careful adherence to guidelines and instructions. The study also uncovered various issues, including weather-related challenges, psychological readiness, lack of insurance coverage for passengers, and concerns among pilots regarding the cultural attitude, high danger, and expensive equipment costs. Furthermore, the research highlights the need for financial assistance for the United Grassroots and Tribes Paragliding Association (UGAT-PAC), the organization overseeing the paragliding site, due to the substantial investment required to develop a fly site. In conclusion, even though paragliding is risky, it can be enjoyed safely through proper preparation, skill development, and adherence to safety measures. The findings of this study contribute valuable insights to enhance the safety and security of paragliding as a recreational activity.

Keywords: *Safety, Security, Paragliding, Recreation, Risk Factors, Safety Precautions, Sports Tourism*

INTRODUCTION

Providing exceptional tourism requires a strong focus on safety and security. The ability to create a safe and secure environment for tourists determines a tourism destination's success or failure more than any other economic activity as stated by the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNTWO, n.d.). Security is the process of making people or places secure. In contrast, safety is the state of being protected against harm or danger (King, 2021). In paragliding, safety entails accident-free flight to prevent sudden interruptions from reducing flight enjoyment. Learning more, developing your talents, and improving your judgement will keep you safe. The only way to grow effectively over time is to fly safely while expanding horizons (Pagen, 2001). The UNWTO defines tourism as "travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment" for pleasure, work, or other reasons. As one of the main drivers of the economies of many nations, tourism frequently draws a large variety of enterprises created particularly to serve tourists from other regions.

The tourism industry has eight different sectors and one of these sectors is activities and attractions (Nour, 2019). Adventure tourism is a particular sector of the travel industry that focuses on experiences that give tourists a chance to have thrilling encounters. Adventure tourism is an immersive experience, enabling visitors to have a physical connection to the location they are visiting (Tjoe, 2021). One of the fastest-growing tourist segments is sports tourism. Whether sports are the major reason for the trip, more and more tourists are interested in participating in sports-related activities while they are away (UNWTO, 2021). Recreation is a necessary part of life that refreshes and rejuvenates a person's body and mind. Recreational activities help a person relax and decrease the effects of work-related and interpersonal stressors. These activities also allow an individual to sharpen communication, time management, motivational and disciplinary skills (studocu.com, 2019).

Ecostinger (2018) explained that Paragliding is an excellent flying sport that allows a pilot to navigate through the air using a small aircraft- the perfect activity for adventurous people. Many people use paragliding as a recreational activity, while others practice paragliding as a highly competitive sport. It is a recreational and competitive sport and a great way to experience the place's natural beauty. Adventurous people opt to go to places where they can paraglide as it is a thrilling sport and a must-have experience. Paragliding has become famous over the past few years, with people taking it up for a great and fulfilling experience. Many consider paragliding one of the world's most thrilling and awe- inspiring activities. Viewing the Earth's colourful terrain from thousands of feet above, dangling from strings, and drifting through the air like a free-floating feather is exhilarating (Gaxiola, 2020). Depending on the source, the history of paragliding inventions varies (Ronca, n.d.). In Dennis Pagen's 2001 book, "The Art of Paragliding," Otto Lilienthal is celebrated as a flight pioneer for his 1880s bat-like wings and over 1000 flights from an artificial hill, which prefigured modern hang gliding. His innovations greatly

influenced the Wright brothers and the course of aviation history. Pierre Bétemps founded the first paragliding school in 1979, and Laurent de Kalbermatten began manufacturing the first wings in 1985. This period marked the beginning of paragliding's rise in popularity, especially in the United States during the late 1980s (United States Hang Gliding and Paragliding Association, n.d.). David Barish's development of the Vortex Ring parachute in 1955 and Domina Jalbert's invention of the Parafoil in the 1960s were pivotal to the evolution of paragliding.

The Philippines' tourism industry is still expanding. Although paragliding is still a new sport in the Philippines, as Medel (2022) noted on Windowseat, there are places to do it. Unbeknownst to many, the Philippines has several paragliding destinations. Paragliding in the Calabarzon Region can be done in Rizal's San Mateo, Cavite's Carmona, and Batangas's Lake Taal region. There are locations in Legazpi, Bicol, and Nueva Vizcaya, all within the broader Luzon area. You may try Oslob, Cebu in the Visayas, which is extremely well-liked by tourists. Sarangani, in Mindanao's South, is where you may find paragliding locations (Mangubat, 2020). Considering that local tourists are unfamiliar with this form of pleasure, evaluating the safety and security of paragliding in the Philippines is now more crucial than ever. Jaojela (n.d.) added that "The Philippines have a lot to offer, not only different breath taking places and outstanding services but also a sport like paragliding"; as a result, the potential of paragliding here in the Philippines will help to increase tourist arrivals for both domestic and foreign arrivals.

Rarely does Nueva Vizcaya appear on the list of Luzon's must-see locations. In reality, the province provides a variety of low- to high-adrenaline sports (Bennett, 2021). One of these activities is paragliding, which is run by Ms. Violet Lucasi- Elrays, founder of the United Grassroots and Tribes Paragliding Association (UGAT-PAC), a corporation of paragliding pilots from different cultural tribes in the Philippines. A team of Indigenous People and home-grown local pilots who dream of becoming professional air sports pilots that can make a mark in the international flying arena, the Philippines native who graduated from the Ateneo de Manila University, a licensed professional pilot, a YouTuber, and the proprietor of a log cabin in the neighbourhood of Sitio Naduntog, brgy. Tiblac, Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya. She acknowledged having mental health issues and how paragliding had helped her overcome them in her interview with Santos (2021). She urged her teacher to go to Nueva Vizcaya to investigate if it could be turned into a paragliding site, and they found that it offers some of the best wind conditions in the Philippines. She also mentioned that Ambaguio has the best geographical location and that not all mountains are good for paragliding. They introduced paragliding in Nueva Vizcaya for training and community development to make it "The Paragliding Mecca of the North," (7641 Island or the Philippines, 2020).

The sport has existed since the early 2000s. However, only a few people participate in it today, most of whom are from Metro Manila, as the sport did not initially take off but eventually gained popularity (Mangubat, 2020). Despite considerable concerns, paragliding is seen by Mitchell (2022) as a safe recreational activity. Like aerial activities, skydiving, hang gliding, and other extreme sports require caution. Without the correct instruction, things can go wrong, and occasionally, people sustain injuries in collisions,

become lost or trapped in distant locations, and are exposed to inclement weather. To reduce the possibility of harm or death, it's critical to take security measures. Familiarity with your equipment improves your ability to comprehend your instructor's communications. You may promptly comply when he commands you to "pull the rear risers" once you know where they are in control lines, risers, a canopy, a leading edge, and a harness (Pagen, 2001). There are several different types of paragliders on sale. They differ in terms of size, weight restrictions, and design. When selecting paragliding equipment, it's crucial to consult with a professional or an experienced pilot to ensure the gear matches your size and skill level. The market offers high-quality used gliders at competitive prices, but they must be in good condition and not overly used to ensure safety. The size of the glider is important; too small and you'll need to run faster for take-off and landing, too large and it may lose stability. For lighter pilots, a smaller glider within the weight range of 55 to 75 kilos is advisable for optimal control and an enjoyable flight experience (Pagen, 2001).

Table 1: Preflight Chart

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Harness straps • Leg straps • Buckles • Harness pack cloth • Seat • Both carabiners • All risers • Back support • Parachute handle • Parachute position 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Parachute bridle ✓ Riser quick links ✓ All lines ✓ Control lines ✓ Control line pulleys ✓ Control line toggles and knot ✓ Canopy material for damage ✓ Canopy debris ✓ Canopy layout (line over) ✓ Helmet
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In paragliding, safety is paramount. Pilots must rigorously adhere to pre-flight checklists to ensure equipment is in optimal condition, as in-flight adjustments are not feasible. Equipment failure is a significant cause of accidents, making routine inspections and emergency preparedness essential. Tandem flights introduce additional weight considerations. It's vital to measure the combined weight of the pilot and passenger to prevent exceeding the canopy's capacity. Selecting a certified canopy that can accommodate the total weight is crucial for a safe paragliding experience (Magar, 2020). Paragliding is accessible to a wide range of ages and physical conditions, not requiring exceptional athleticism (Pagen, 2001). Regular participation in paragliding naturally improves muscle strength and control over the equipment. For optimal physical fitness, focus on leg exercises and ankle strengthening through uneven terrain running. Hydration is crucial, so drink water every 45 minutes (Adrenaline Parapente, n.d.).

Table 2: Unfavourable Weather and its Risk Description

	Risk Title	Risk Description
Unfavourable Weather	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rainy Day• Cloudy Day• Strong Wind	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Failure to achieve and retain sufficient lift• Loss of control• Unable to fly in the planned direction• Unable to land in the planned landing zone or unable to land safely anywhere• Being struck by lightning• Getting pulled up into a cloud• Light or heavy injuries or even death

One of the risk variables is the environment at the flight location. There aren't many places to land in an emergency when flying from rocky or difficult terrain. Additionally, sites with no wind indicators are to be avoided. The priority regulations should also be considered if the location should also be considered as packed (Adrenaline Parapente, 2021).

Table 3: Environment and its Risk Description

	Risk Title	Risk Description
Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rocky or Rough• Terrain Sites without wind indicators• Overcrowded site	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emergency landing areas were limited• Unable to land safely• Lost and stuck in an unfamiliar place• Banging into objects such as trees, mountains or other pilots• Can't paraglide back to the take-off area• Light or heavy injuries or even death

It appeared that increased flying hours exposed pilots to a slight increase in risk, contrary to the belief that more flying reduces risk. Pilot errors in glider control and in decision-making, not in equipment malfunction, were the key issues, consistent with other disciplines. Future safety interventions should focus on improving back protection, pilot training, and glider control and encouraging timely reserve parachute deployment (Wilkes, et. al. 2022). Without the appropriate technical knowledge to execute these maneuvers successfully, pilots run significant dangers while in the air. Various factors may cause a paragliding accident. Pilot error, equipment malfunction, and unfavourable weather conditions are the most frequent causes of paragliding injuries. The main factor in paragliding accidents is pilot mistakes. It usually happens upon launching. This can also involve failing to follow protocol, making errors when landing, soaring, or trying maneuvers beyond your rating. One of the least likely reasons for accidents is equipment failure. This may involve faulty machinery or issues with the wing itself Mitchell (2022).

Table 4: Technical Expertise and its Risk Description

Risk Title		Risk Description
Technical Expertise	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Equipment failure• Pilot error• Poor decision making	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Banging into objects such as trees, mountains, or other pilots• Falling out of the sky• Getting lost• Running into bad weather conditions• Mistakes in take-off, soaring, and landing• Malfunctioning equipment• Light or heavy injuries or even death

An experienced pilot has the necessary credentials, insurance, and safety protocols. The USHPA establishes paragliding standards and gives pilots access to training materials. Pilot must finish an approved training course and pass a competency test to get certified. The USHPA also provides paraglider ratings, which show the pilot's level of training and experience. To be approved, your powered paraglider, powered paramotor, or paraglider must complete a series of tests administered by an aviation body. These evaluations assess performance, control, and stability (Mitchell, 2022). The only organization recognized by our Network Access Control (NAC) to issue national permits for paragliding and hang gliding with the International Pilot Proficiency Identification (IPPI) equivalent printed on them is the Philippine Paragliding and Hang-Gliding Association, Inc. (PPHGA). Visitor pilots are advised to carry their IPPI card along with their national license, certificate, or rating granted by their federations. They may apply for a PPHGA license. Filipino pilots are encouraged to have a national license issued by PPHGA, Inc. To safely operate the National Airspace System, pilots must also be conversant with the Civil Aviation Authority of the Philippines (CAAP) laws and airspace classifications (FAI, 2018).

The purpose of conducting the study is to raise awareness about the safety and security of paragliding in Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya as a recreational activity, thereby, potentially contributing to the promotion of paragliding as part of the tourism destination's activities and further assisting in the drive for a more dynamic and vibrant Tourism industry of Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines.

Table 5: *The Paradigm of the Study*

Research Objectives

This study explored the paragliding challenges encountered in Sitio Naduntog, Barangay Tiblac, Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines as a recreational activity for the second semester of 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought to find answers to the following objectives:

1. To enumerate and discuss the risk factors of paragliding as a recreational activity.
 2. To determine the safety precautions and security observed in paragliding as a recreational activity.
 3. To document related issues about paragliding as a recreational activity.
 4. To give recommendations on the safety and security of paragliding as a recreational activity based on the study results.
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers employed a qualitative descriptive method to interpret the collected data. This study utilized a group interview approach guided by a questionnaire focused on assessing the safety and security aspects of paragliding as a recreational activity in Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in Sitio Naduntog, Barangay Tiblac, Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, located a 30-minute drive from the provincial capital of Bayombong. This area

serves as the site for paragliding activities and where the study's informants are based. The study was conducted in the first quarter of 2023.

Informants of the Study

Participants included nine experienced pilots who met specific criteria: each had completed a minimum of 40 solo or tandem flights, received training at three or more fly sites, held a PG1 license, and were active members of UGAT-PAC in Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Pilots who did not meet these qualifications or opted out of participation voluntarily were excluded. This selection ensured a cohort well-versed in paragliding practices, contributing to the study's insights into their experiences and safety measures.

Table 6: List of Pilots with Corresponding Flight Records as of March 21, 2023

Pilot	Hours of Flight	No. of Flight	No. of Flysite	Flysites	Level of licensed
ALLEN EDWARD GAYO Airsports Academy Scholar	6.8	40	2	Tiblac, Ambaguio	PG1
				Sarangani	
NESTOR LOGMAYO JR. Airsports Academy Scholar	7.5	50	3	Tiblac, Ambaguio	PG1
				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Sarangani	
ZURIEL LUCASI Airsports Academy Scholar	10	50	3	Tiblac, Ambaguio	PG1
				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Sarangani	
FRANCIS MORALES Airsports Academy Scholar	18	65	3	Tiblac, Ambaguio	PG1
				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Sarangani	
ALY PUGONG Airsports Academy Scholar	25	120	5	Tiblac, Ambaguio	PG2
				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Sarangani	
				Nongkhai, Thailand	
				KCH Lahn, Thailand	
SERI PUGONG Airsports Academy Scholar	26	125	5	Tiblac, Ambaguio	PG2
				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Sarangani	
				Nongkhai, Thailand	
				KCH Lahn, Thailand	
MARTES BUGTONG	28	185	6	Highlander, Bayombong	PG2
				Bangan Hill	
				Tiblac, Ambaguio	

Solo Pilot Ambaguio, PDP Batch 1				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Cardona, Rizal	
				Sarangani	
KELVIN LIYANGNA Solo and Tandem Pilot Airsports Academy Scholar	200+	230 Solo Flight 210 Tandem Flight	11	Tiblac, Ambaguio	T2
				Highlander, Bayombong	
				Bangan Hill, Bambang	
				Diadi	
				Nagtipunan, Quirino	
				Carmona, Rizal	
				Sarangani	
				South Cotabato	
				Ranau, Malaysia	
				Nongkhai, Thailand	
KCH Lahrn, Thailand					

Table 6 shows the eight pilots of UGAT-PAC with corresponding flight records as of March 21, 2023. Divided into six columns, the pilots’ flight hours, number of flights, number of fly sites, and their license level. 8 Pilots belong to the IPs from the different municipalities of Nueva Vizcaya. 4 pilots have PG1 or Novice IPPI Para2 license 6.8-18 hours for 40-65 flights in 2-5 different fly site, three pilots have PG2 or Independent IPPI Para3 license, 25-28 hours for 120-185 flights in 5-6 different fly site and one pilot have a T2 license or Commercial Tandem Pilot, 200 plus flying hours for 230 solo flights and 210 tandem flights in 11 different fly sites. Among the four local Pilots, 3 of them competed abroad (Thailand and Malaysia), representing the Philippines. Nueva Vizcaya Paragliding (2023) posted, “This start of the year has led us to finally pay off and acquire our international SPORTING LICENSE for 4 Indigenous Pilots (IPs) for 2023. This sporting license allows them to compete internationally and represent their hometowns (Ambaguio-Bayombong), the province of Nueva Vizcaya, and the Philippines”.

Participants included nine experienced pilots who met specific criteria: each had completed a minimum of 40 solo or tandem flights, received training at three or more fly sites, held a PG1 license, and were active members of UGAT-PAC in Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Pilots who did not meet these qualifications or opted out of participation voluntarily were excluded. This selection ensured a cohort well-versed in paragliding practices, contributing to the study's insights into their experiences and safety measures.

Research Instrument

The technical panel of experts and the research coordinator validate the research instruments. The researchers used group interviews and a guide questionnaire as the main instruments in this study to provide and gather as much information as possible for relevant evaluation. It was used to determine the safety and security of paragliding as a recreational Activity in Sitio Naduntog, Barangay Tiblac, Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Prior to conducting the study, informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring their voluntary participation and understanding of the study's purpose. The participants were informed that all gathered information would be treated confidentially. The study aimed to explore three main aspects of paragliding as a

recreational activity through semi-structured interviews. Firstly, participants were asked to enumerate and discuss risk factors associated with paragliding. Secondly, safety precautions and security measures observed in paragliding were explored. Lastly, participants were prompted to share any additional issues related to paragliding as a recreational activity. Interviews were conducted in person to facilitate detailed responses from each informant.

Table 7. Specifications of Interview Guide Questions aligned with Reviewed Related Studies and Literature

Objectives of the study	Interview guide questions	Related Studies and Literature
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To enumerate and discuss the risk factors relating to paragliding as a recreational activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What are the common risk factors in paragliding you encountered as a pilot? ● What is the risk of paragliding in unfavorable weather like rainy, cloudy, and windy days? ● What risk do you encounter here (Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya) as your paragliding environment? ● What is the risk of paragliding in a rocky or rough terrain? ● What is the risk of paragliding in an overcrowded site? ● What is the risk of paragliding without having the necessary expertise? ● What is the risk of equipment failure, pilot error, or poor decision-making in paragliding? ● What is the risk of not wearing proper clothes in paragliding? ● Does weight matter in paragliding? If so, what is the desired weight in solo and tandem flights? ● Does strength matter in paragliding? If so, what are the desired strengths in solo and tandem flights? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cameron (2020) ● Adrenaline Parapente (2021) ● Wilkes et al. (2020) ● Magar (2020) ● Mitchell (2022) ● Pagen (2019)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● To determine the safety precautions and security observed in paragliding as a recreational activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What are the safety precautions and security that you do before, during, and after paragliding? ● What are the dos and don'ts before, during, and after paragliding? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Magar (2020) ● King (2021) ● Pagen (2019)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the best conditions for paragliding as a recreational activity? • What is the paragliding equipment that you use? Why are these important? • What are the gears that you use? 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To document related issues about paragliding as a recreational activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What issues or problems have you encountered in the conduct of paragliding as a recreational activity? • Kindly narrate or describe these encountered issues. • How did you solve or address these encountered issues? 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To give recommendations on the Safety and Security of Paragliding as a Recreational Activity base on the result of the study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What recommendations do you suggest to avoid possible issues or problems that may occur in the future about paragliding? 	

Data gathering Procedure

The researchers administered the instrument to the informants through an on-site visit and a group interview. The following was the procedure the proponents used in gathering data:

1. The research Instrument was validated and approved by the panel of evaluators and the University Research Ethics Board (UREB). Certification was given to approve and validate the paper and research instrument.
2. Booked an appointment for paragliding through Nueva Vizcaya Paragliding official page.
3. On-site visits were made for the researchers to try paragliding themselves, and then the informants' consent was asked for participation, and a schedule was set based on their available time for the interview.
4. Another on-site visit to proceed with the group interview, depending on the available Pilot on the agreed time and date at the Paragliding site in Sitio Naduntog, Barangay Tiblac, Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, for at least an hour.
5. Another on-site visit and interview if some of the informants are unavailable or data gathering is not yet done.
6. Data was evaluated, interpreted, and treated after the data was gathered.
7. After analyzing and interpreting the data, recommendations were given based on the study.

Treatment of Data

This study utilized information gathered from the interview: these are the time of visit and group interview. Thematic analysis treatment was used to treat the data and was arranged according to the components presented in the objective of the problem.

RESULTS

Section 1. Risk Factors Relating to Paragliding as a Recreational Activity

Table 8. Risk factors in paragliding the pilots encountered

RESPONSES	Frequency	Percentage
Flying with low-level skills and accountability.	5	55%
Flying with poor knowledge of weather and terrain.	2	22%
Weight	1	11%
Strength	1	11%

Section 2. Safety Precautions and Security Observed in Paragliding as a Recreational Activity

Table 9. The do's and don'ts in tandem and solo flight before, during and after paragliding as a Recreational Activity.

DO'S AND DON'T'S BEFORE PARAGLIDING	
TANDEM	SOLO PILOT
<p style="text-align: center;">DO's</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Book a flight or walk-in • Wear appropriate clothing • Bring personal necessities, snacks, and entertainment • Receive proper orientation • Ensure both pilots and passengers are mentally, emotionally, and physically prepared • Check and prepare gears and equipment • Assess the wind conditions and wait for favorable wind 	<p style="text-align: center;">DO'S</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Book a flight and bring gears and equipment (incoming pilot) • Tandem with a local pilot to assess and familiarize with the fly site, landing site, terrain, and weather • Wear appropriate clothing • Be mentally, emotionally and physically prepared • Use suitable equipment • Check and prepare gears and equipment • Assess the wind conditions and wait for good wind
<p style="text-align: center;">DON'T'S</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schedule important meetings on the 	<p style="text-align: center;">DON'T'S</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forgetting the gear and equipment

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> flight date Eating a huge meal Not getting enough sleep Wearing inappropriate clothing Stepping on or touching the pilots' equipment Arriving late or not showing up on the scheduled date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being mentally, emotionally, or physically unstable Not checking the equipment or gears before launching Leaving the gears and equipment unattended Not getting enough sleep Flying at night
DO'S AND DON'T'S DURING PARAGLIDING	
TANDEM	SOLO PILOT
DO's	DO'S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pilot focuses on maneuvers and entertains the passenger while ensuring the passenger sits comfortably and enjoys flying. Maintain proper airspeed. Passengers can shout, scream, and talk to the pilot. Raise or leg-up during landing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain proper airspeed Be alert and aware of the surroundings at all times Land safely
DON'T'S	DON'T'S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jump, sit, and stop running during the launch. Looking down too much, moving too much, and touching the control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flying without assessing the wind Flying during strong or weak wind Reckless flying while on air Reckless landing
DO'S AND DON'T'S AFTER PARAGLIDING	
TANDEM	SOLO PILOT
DO's	DO'S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The pilot checks or asks the passenger if they are okay, and checks the gear and equipment before storing it properly. Wait for the car if the landing area is in the Jamboree Site, Masoc, Bayombong Nueva, Vizcaya. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the whole body for possible injuries Check and store equipment properly. Wait for the car if the landing area is in the Jamboree Site, Masoc, Bayombong Nueva, Vizcaya.
DON'T'S	DON'T'S
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wandering or leaving the landing area in Jamboree Site, Masoc, Bayombong Nueva, Vizcaya Touching, stepping, or playing with the pilots' equipment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do not wander or leave the landing area at the Jamboree Site, Masoc, Bayombong Nueva, Vizcaya.

Section 3: Related Issues On Paragliding as a Recreational Activity.

The study found that the issues faced by tandem passengers include dependency on weather, psychological preparedness of passengers, and lack of insurance coverage. On the other hand, paragliding pilots in Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, face some challenges, such as the high cost of equipment and over all training and operations, lack of proper training, and character behavior on wanting quick results. In addition, issues

related to fly site development include high costs associated with establishing outdoor destinations.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 depicts that 5 (55%) of the responses indicate flying with low-level skills and accountability was one of the risk factors of paragliding. As stated by Pilot Aly, “The risk of the environment in Ambaguio is its height, which is too high for beginners. Therefore, beginners cannot fly here since the landing spot is too far away. Similarly, some pilots do not reach the landing when the wind is weak. The wind is also gusty, which is fine, but it may also be turbulent and dangerous for flying.” She also stated, “It is risky and prone to mishaps without the necessary experience or training. For example, foreign pilots who claimed to be expert pilots came to fly here, yet an accident occurred. They dangled from a tree and never arrived at the landing zone. Examining the environment (fly site, landing area) is vital. Your ability level must meet the required skill level to fly in that place because many things might go wrong if you lack flight training and knowledge.” Although learning to fly is a lot of fun, it must be done with a safe, educational program. The best course of action is to train under a reputable, knowledgeable instructor. The demands can be best met by the instructor, who can customize the classes. Afterwards, start on ground training and lessons with tandem instruction or move from flat groundwork to actual flying and glider control from various heights. The instructor or local guide familiarizes students with paragliding by showing them the actual flying place or using films and images. Someone prone to accidents is probably negligent or has little regard for their safety such as a pilot paraglider without the requisite training. In that case, they will not be able to control the glider, take off or land effectively and will make bad landing decisions (Pagen,2001).

Two (22%) of the responses indicate that flying with poor knowledge of weather and terrain is another risk factor of paragliding thus pilots need to learn and be knowledgeable about the different types of weather and terrain of a fly site. As mentioned by Pilot Kevin, “The wind is strong when it is raining. It is not good for paragliding because you are more likely to get harmed.” Pilot Ally also said that, “The first risk factor is the wind, as we cannot control the wind directions. Another risk is the slope of the take-off or fly site area. There are times when the slope is tough for take-offs, but there are also times when it is easy. If the terrain is rocky and an emergency landing is required, it is hazardous, especially for the pilot, because even if you followed the proper landing procedure, any part of your body can be hurt as the landing place is rocky.” Unpredictable weather poses a serious risk that shouldn't be disregarded. Some of these are heavy rain, strong winds, clouds or fog, excessively warm or cold temperatures, poor visibility, and sudden weather changes when flying (Cameron, 2020). Gusty means a sudden strong wind.

Last March 12, 2023, the researcher scheduled a flight at 11 a.m. and experienced gusty wind during landing. The pilot tried to land several times but failed due to gusty wind. As a result, the flying time extended to 20 to 30 minutes. The wind is usually quiet through the night and becomes stronger by 9 or 10 in the morning. The sun's heat agitates the

environment, and it is responsible for this. By late afternoon, the wind peaks, and by nightfall, it starts to diminish (Pagen,2001). One of the risk variables is the environment where the flight will take place. There won't be many places to land safely if you come from rocky or harsh terrain (Adrenaline Parapente,2021). The slope's steepness ranges from 10 to 20 degrees, allowing you to dash at takeoff speeds. The training location should ideally be high enough for you to climb the slope gradually. The ideal hill is becoming increasingly rare since we don't live in a perfect world, and the land is getting harder to come by. Therefore, most schools employ some hills to accommodate varying wind directions and ability levels. The instructor pointed out each lesson's appropriate location to the pilot (Pagen,2001).

The data reveals that 11% weight is a risk factor. The heavier the person, the harder it is to control lines. However, wings have sizes that can accommodate different weights. The desired weight is not more than 100kg for both solo and tandem. Pilot Kelvin stated that "For each weight, there is a particular wing range. The larger the wing, the greater the weight, and vice versa. Weight is an important component. For example, if I am light and my wing is large, the air will easily carry me away." A small glider will require faster running during takeoff and landing. Use caution when utilizing equipment, especially if you're inexperienced, because you might not know how to evaluate its quality or suitability for your needs based on size. Before using a new glider or harness, please seek professional advice on whether it suits your size and ability level (Pagen,2001).

The length of the wing also affects the minimum weight for paragliding. It is preferable to choose a smaller- sized paraglider if you are small-framed. The lightest paraglider can carry between 121 and 165 pounds (55 to 75 kilos). Problems associated with being under the minimum weight include wing collapses and decreased control. Paragliders use the forces of gravity, high winds, and glider wing power to maintain flight. Each paraglider will, therefore have a maximum and minimum weight range depending on size. Certain single paragliders have been specifically engineered to carry more oversized loads. There are logical and practical justifications for the weight restrictions. Paragliding uses gravity and wind force, as was already established. You will profit immensely if you precisely weigh the paraglider load and don't overload it because you can fly longer and travel farther (Mark, 2019). Weight implies that the pilot should maintain a healthy weight to reduce the risk of injury during take-off and landing. Pilots should use suitable equipment based on their skills and weight.

Findings suggest that strength is also a risk factor, with 11%. Paragliding is primarily a sports activity. Pilots are athletes and strength training is part of the course. Pilots should be fit enough to raise their wings and run. Pilot Ally stated that strength matters, "Yes, soaring solo in a weaker state influences your decision." Because you'll be carrying the glider and ascending hills at first, the physical effort required for paragliding's first stages is frequently the highest. Naturally, this technique is more straightforward for you if you are in better form.

Eat well before you work out. This calls for a hearty breakfast and many carbohydrates (starches like potatoes, pasta, or bread) the night before. Exercises that increase

endurance through aerobics and flexibility training are advised. To enable total muscle usage, stretching activities that limber you up are prescribed (Pagen,2001). While flying the wing, having upper, solid body muscles is advantageous. The arm muscles will strengthen as you fly and maneuver the wing. Flexibility, mobility, and range of motion are all improved and increased. The upper body strength will increase as you exercise and participate in the sport more. This will help control the paraglider more effectively and strengthen the arm muscles. Although arm strength is essential for controlling the glider, lower body strength is needed to accelerate because it's a must to push on a speed bar with legs. This implies that strength is required in paragliding. The pilot should be strong Enough to carry the gears and equipment, flexible enough in an emergency requiring flexibility, stamina for continuous training, strong legs and ankles for landing, and strong muscles to maneuver in the air and lastly, the pilot should eat properly.

Table 2 highlights similarities and differences in procedures for tandem and solo paragliding flights. While both types share general safety protocols, tandem flights require additional steps for gear preparation and passenger management. Adherence to strict safety precautions before, during, and after paragliding is crucial to ensure a smooth, safe, and enjoyable flight experience. These precautions include thorough checks of terrain, weather conditions, equipment, take-off and landing sites, strict adherence to instructor or guide instructions, wearing appropriate protective gear and clothing, and avoiding risky maneuvers or distractions. By following these guidelines, paragliders can significantly reduce the risk of accidents and injuries while maximizing the joy and fulfillment of soaring through the sky. When approached with proper preparation and caution, paragliding, despite its inherent risks, can be safely enjoyed.

Paragliding requires mental preparation or anxiety management, as with most physically demanding activities. The whole point is to progressively learn to operate the glider while controlling danger to reduce anxiety. In essence, a fear of heights is a fear of falling. You could be high while feeling confident and fearless (Pagen,2001).

Upon arriving at the fly site, staff or the safety guards help the first passenger put on safety gear and help the pilot prepare the equipment while waiting for the good wind. The paragliding gear includes a helmet, windbreakers, shoes, gloves, a facemask (made of fabric), a chest belt, a waist belt, a leg belt, and a knee pad. The Paragliding equipment includes a reserve parachute, a canopy (wing), a harness, a variometer, radios, airspeed indicators, an altimeter, risers, and lines (Pagen,2001). Pilot Kelvin asserted that, "The leg belt is essential because it holds you in place after you ran for takeoff. You must always double-check if the equipment is still in good condition because once you're at the top, you must consider the reality that your one foot is in the pit, so you must always double- check." Pilot Ally mentioned that, when doing an emergency landing, not wearing adequate clothing is dangerous. For example, you are safe while dangling from a tree, but you will have bruises and scrapes as a result of wearing inappropriate clothing, such as shorts." Therefore, it is crucial to wear appropriate clothing that shields passengers from the sun's heat and provides protection against potential scratches or bruises that may occur due to incidental contact with hard surfaces or similar objects.

Finding and fixing equipment and gear issues on the ground is much easier than doing it in the air. Every safe flight must include a preflight check. From this point on, it should be included in your launch and layout procedures. All of the glider's critical components are examined for integrity as part of the preflight examination. A pre-flight inspection is performed to evaluate your glider for wear and damage and ensure that all preparations have been made for it to fly (Pagen,2001).

At the fly site, only one passenger and staff member are permitted to enter to ensure minimal crowding and enhance safety for both people and equipment. Adjacent to the paragliding site's left side is a designated waiting area where passengers' families and friends can observe the flights. The pilot inflates the canopy when wind conditions are favorable and directs the passenger to run. Both pilot and passenger run together, supported by additional pilots on either side acting as "para boys" to aid in take-off. Passengers are instructed to refrain from jumping, sitting, or stopping during the launch process. Pilot Kelvin noted that, "Guests at Sky Escape 360 are not permitted to enter the fly site, especially during operations. This strict rule is in place to prevent accidents, as there is a high risk of the canopy (wing) hitting them if they are present during pilot landings. For their safety, guests must remain in the designated waiting area at the fly site or within Sky Escape 360."

During flight, pilots focus on maneuvering and attending to passengers, while passengers enjoy a comfortable ride. They can relax, capture video or photos using a GoPro by adjusting it horizontally or vertically, voice concerns or comments, inform the pilot of any discomfort (such as dizziness), converse with the pilot, and appreciate the scenery and the flight. Passengers should refrain from looking downward excessively, moving excessively, or touching the controls. Solo pilots should avoid flying without assessing the wind conditions, flying in strong or weak winds, engaging in reckless flying, and landings. Favorable wind conditions allowed the take-off area to double as the landing site. However, in cases of weak wind, landings were directed to the Jamboree Site in Masoc, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. After landing, a vehicle transported the pilot and passenger back to the log cabin, where initial orientation and payment procedures took place. It is recommended that neither the pilot nor the passenger stray from the designated landing site after touchdown.

Section 3. Paragliding is a sport that requires dedication, patience, and passion. Paragliding pilots can enjoy this sport safely and responsibly by following the proper process and caring for the equipment. To overcome these challenges, United Grassroots and Tribes Paragliding Association (UGAT-PAC), a local organization, has developed a curriculum and a system to provide quality education and support for aspiring and experienced pilots. UGAT- PAC also raises funds and uses 100% of the income from tandem operations to support the training of pilots.

Weather forecasts may differ from actual conditions, which cannot be controlled. Passengers may become frustrated if unable to fly on the scheduled date and sometimes disregard crew decisions, such as cancellations due to stormy or rainy weather, restrictions on heavy passengers, or rescheduling for optimal wind conditions. To mitigate

these challenges, pilots and staff provide comprehensive pre-flight information online and conduct thorough orientations. Passengers also often experience anxiety and fear, particularly upon arrival at the flight site. Crew members, including pilots and staff, undergo training to effectively manage and alleviate passenger anxieties and fears, ensuring a comforting and reassuring experience.

Another significant issue is the absence of insurance coverage for paragliding in the Philippines, as it is classified as an extreme sport and lacks third-party insurers willing to provide coverage. To ensure passenger safety, tandem flights are exclusively conducted with licensed and experienced pilots. Presently, among the 13 pilots, only one IP pilot holds a T2 license, enabling them to pilot tandem or commercial flights. The remaining pilots possess licenses ranging from pre-PG1 to PG2 levels.

Additionally, the paragliding sport is subject to taxation, despite misconceptions that it brings substantial wealth to pilots in Nueva Vizcaya. In reality, the operational costs including equipment and training expenses, are exceptionally high. To address these challenges, partnerships have been formed with locals to plant grasses at the fly site. This initiative not only aims to mitigate erosion but also promotes an advocacy where 100% of the proceeds contribute to empowering Indigenous Peoples (IP) and local pilots. The IP Pilot recommends proper training and education to avoid potential issues in paragliding. It's advised not to fast-track education, only work with reputable instructors, fly with experienced pilots, adhere to all checklists, invest in the right equipment, establish a proven operational system, and develop a top-tier fly site. Training pilots with values focused on quality rather than profit is crucial. However, this does not negate the importance of safety and security. Any professional paragliding instructor will provide essential safety tips for paragliding. Like any sport or activity, paragliding has rules and regulations in place to enhance pilot safety and security and protect those in the vicinity. While paragliding offers an exhilarating experience accessible to everyone, even a minor mistake can lead to serious injuries and damages. Experienced flyers typically have a thorough understanding of these rules to prioritize safety for themselves and others. Paragliding, is a safe activity if you learn with a good instructor.

Section 4. Paragliding is a thrilling sport that requires proper health and education, equipment, and guidance. The UGAT-PAC should build a strong and lasting partnership with the local community and develop a high-class fly site for paragliding activities. To achieve this, the UGAT-PAC should seek the assistance of the regional officials and the DOT, train pilots with spiritual values, and organize fundraising events online and offline. A first-aid package and a paragliding pharmacy must be readily available for emergency medical assistance in case of an accident. In case of an incident, responsible authorities should be notified promptly using an accessible contact list, emergency radios, whistles, and emergency flares. Identify and designate at least one additional landing spot in case of emergencies, enabling pilots to land quickly and safely if needed. To create mutual benefits and cross-promotion, the DOT can facilitate partnerships between local paragliding pilots and tourism-related businesses, such as hotels, resorts, and travel agencies. Organizing fundraising events can help promote paragliding by planning and hosting events such as paragliding competitions, airshows, or awareness campaigns to

raise funds. Engage with local communities, sponsors, and aviation enthusiasts to generate financial support through this sports activity and the Department of Tourism partnership. Finally, the DOT can support infrastructure development, such as dedicated launch sites, landing zones, and safety facilities, to ensure a safer and more convenient experience for pilots and tourists.

Conclusions

It is concluded that paragliding, while not entirely risk-free, is not disproportionately dangerous compared to other recreational activities or forms of aviation. Paragliding is a thrilling and rewarding recreational activity requiring strict and careful execution and preparation before, during, and after. As enthusiast explore new locations and opportunities, adherence to safety protocols, proper training, and awareness of personal limitations mitigate risks and ensure the continued enjoyment and viability of paragliding as a recreational pursuit. Lastly, Nueva Vizcaya Paragliding has no record of major accidents, making it a safe environment for recreational paragliding.

Recommendations

Further research is recommended to expand and explore different settings, contexts, perspectives, conditions and cultures. In extent focusing on enhancing safety protocols and risk management strategies identifying gaps or inconsistencies that may affect safety, accessibility, or sustainability of paragliding and other sports activities, and further investigate the effectiveness of different safety gear, training methods, and emergency procedures to improve overall participant safety and security. For the Tourism Management and the Hospitality Management Curricula to be integrate topic in Risk Management as Applied to Safety, Security, and Sanitation, tour and travel Operations and Tourism marketing subjects. For paragliding sites also to be added as destinations in the Tour Guiding course as students can learn about safety protocols, regulations, and best practices for guiding tourists in these environments.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed ethical guidelines by obtaining consent from nine experienced paragliding pilots in Ambaguio, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, who met specific criteria, and securing approval from the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMU-REB). There was no conflict of interest that could affect the integrity of the study's findings, which aimed to fulfill academic requirements and conduct research. Confidentiality was maintained through data anonymization and secure storage, ensuring participant identities were protected. Vulnerable participants were handled sensitively, ensuring voluntary participation and data security. Participants did not receive direct benefits, while the study aimed to assess paragliding safety and security as a recreational activity, acknowledging risks such as COVID-19 to both researchers and participants.

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